

MORPHOLOGY IS A PROCESS OF LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

¹Jalolova Yulduz Mukhiddin kizi,

²Bozorboyeva Farog'at Jamoliddin kizi,

³Ernazarov Sanjar Nurali o'g'li,

⁴Amrullayeva Havasgul Amrulla qizi,

¹Jizzakh State Pedagogical Institute

Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, Tutor,

²Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

Faculty of Pedagogy and Psychology

Second stage student of speech therapy,

³Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

Faculty of Pedagogy and Psychology

Second-level student of sign language pedagogy,

⁴Teacher of the 16th school of Jizzakh city.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7273810>

Annotatsiya:

Morphology is the sub-field of linguistics that studies the internal structure of words. Morphology gives you an idea about the source of the words with rules and regulations on how to form new words. Morphemes are the smallest units of language that carry meaning or function.

Kalit so'zlar: morphology, language, words, acquisition, teaching.

Teaching foreign languages in Uzbekistan has become very important since the first days of the Independence of our country, which pays much attention to the rising of education level of people, their intellectual growth. As first President of Uzbekistan I. A. Karimov said: –Today it's difficult to revalue the importance of knowing foreign languages for our country as our people see their great prosperous future in the cooperation with foreign partners. Paying attention to the importance and value of the teaching foreign languages in the country, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. Karimov said the following: –We should process the creation of the progressive methodic of teaching foreign languages on the national basis in our country.¹

As for the criterion according to which the word is identified as a minimal sign capable of functioning alone (the word understood as the "smallest free form", or interpreted as the "potential minimal sentence"), it is irrelevant for the bulk of functional words which cannot be used "independently" even in elliptical responses.

In spite of the shown difficulties, however, there remains the unquestionable fact that each speaker has at his disposal a ready stock of

¹ Karimov I. A. O'zbekiston buyuk kelajak sari. - T.: O'zbekiston, 1999. - 684 b.

naming units (more precisely, units standing to one another in nominative correlation) by which he can build up an infinite number of utterances reflecting the ever changing situations of reality.

This circumstance urges us to seek the identification of the word as a lingual unit-type on other lines than the "strictly operational definition". In fact, we do find the clarification of the problem in taking into consideration the difference between the two sets of lingual phenomena: on the one hand, "polar" phenomena; on the other hand, "intermediary" phenomena.

Within a complex system of interrelated elements, polar phenomena are the most clearly identifiable, they stand to one another in an utterly unambiguous opposition. Intermediary phenomena are located in the system in between the polar phenomena, making up a gradation of transitions or the so-called "continuum". By some of their properties intermediary phenomena are similar or near to one of the corresponding poles, while by other properties they are similar to the other, opposing pole. The analysis of the intermediary phenomena from the point of view of their relation to the polar phenomena reveal their own status in the system. At the same time this kind of analysis helps evaluate the definitions of the polar phenomena between which a continuum is established.

Morphology is the sub-field of linguistics that studies the internal structure of words. Morphology gives you an idea about the source of the words with rules and regulations on how to form new words. Morphemes are the smallest units of language that carry meaning or function. Chomsky² argued that morphology was interesting because, by using them any speaker can «make infinite use of finite means». The knowledge of morphology is necessary in order to know the way the human brain works and processes language. It will help to produce new alternatives to learn languages, which are more economical in time. Learning morphology is similar to the learning of the other grammatical components. First, we have to internalize lexical entries, later the contact with language makes the learner understand that some words have transparent internal structure generated by the rules of the language, which allow the speakers to coin their own derived and compound words. Word formation produces changes, visible or invisible, whose result is a new complex or compound unit. The subject and the topic of morphology facilitates in several ways to master the language including spelling, vocabulary, fluency, word recognition, pronunciation.

² Иванова И. П., Булакова В. В., Почепцов Г. Г. Теоретическая грамматика современного английского языка. М., 1981.- 312с

We do not know much about the origin of language and, consequently, of the origin of words. It is true that there are several hypotheses, some of them no less fantastic than the theory of the divine origin of language. We know nothing — or almost nothing — about the mechanism by which a speaker's mental process is converted into sound groups called "words", nor about the reverse process whereby a listener's brain converts the acoustic phenomena into concepts and ideas, thus establishing a two-way process of communication. We know very little about the nature of relations between the word and the referent (i. e. object, phenomenon, quality, action, etc. denoted by the word). If we assume that there is a direct relation between the word and the referent — which seems logical — it gives rise to another question: how should we explain the fact that the same referent is designated by quite different sound groups in different languages. We are accidental about the vocabulary of the language; that each word is a small unit within a vast, efficient and perfectly balanced system. But we do not know why it possesses these qualities, nor do we know much about the processes by which it has acquired them.³

The list of unknowns could be extended, but it is probably high time to look at do know by now — though with vague uncertainty — that there is nothing the brighter side and register some of the things we do know about the nature of the word. First, we do know that the word is a unit of speech which, as such, serves the purposes of human communication. Thus, the word can be defined as a unit of communication. Secondly, the word can be perceived as the total of the sounds which comprise it. Third, the word, viewed structurally, possesses several characteristics. The modern approach to word studies is based on distinguishing between the external and the internal structures of the word. By the vocabulary of a language is understood the total sum of its words. Words can serve the purposes of human communication solely due to their meanings, and it is most unfortunate when this fact is ignored by some contemporary scholars who, in their obsession with the fetish of structure tend to condemn as irrelevant anything that eludes mathematical analysis. And this is exactly what meaning, with its subtle variations and shifts, is apt to do.

The formal unity of the word can best be illustrated by comparing a word and a word-group comprising identical constituents. The difference between a blackbird and a black bird is best explained by their relationship with the grammatical system of the language. The word blackbird, which is characterized by unity, possesses a single grammatical framing: blackbird/s. The first

³ Арнольд И. В. Стилистика современного английского языка: Стилистика декодирования. 2-е изд., перераб. Л., 1981.-253с

constituent black is not subject to any grammatical changes. In the word-group a black bird each constituent can acquire grammatical forms of its own: the blackest birds I've ever seen. Other words can be inserted between the components which is impossible so far as the word is concerned as it would violate its unity: a black night bird.

The same example may be used to illustrate what we mean by semantic unity. In the word-group a black bird each of the meaningful words conveys a separate concept: bird — a kind of living creature; black — a color. The word blackbird conveys only one concept: the type of bird. This is one of the main features of any word: it always conveys one concept, no matter how many component morphemes it may have in its external structure. A further structural feature of the word is its susceptibility to grammatical employment. In speech most words can be used in different grammatical forms in which their interrelations are realized.⁴

So far we have only underlined the word's major peculiarities, but this suffices to convey the general idea of the difficulties and questions faced by the scholar attempting to give a detailed definition of the word. The difficulty does not merely consist in the considerable number of aspects that are to be taken into account, but, also, in the essential unanswered questions of word theory which concern the nature of its meaning. All that we have said about the word can be summed up as follows. The word is a speech unit used for the purposes of human communication, materially representing a group of sounds, possessing a meaning, susceptible to grammatical employment and characterized by formal and semantic unity.

There are two levels of approach to the study of word- structure: the level of morphemic analysis and the level of derivational or word-formation analysis. Word is the principal and basic unit of the language system, the largest on the morphologic and the smallest on the syntactic plane of linguistic analysis. 8

It has been universally acknowledged that a great many words have a composite nature and are made up of morphemes, the basic units on the morphemic level, which are defined as the smallest indivisible two-facet language units.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Karimov I. A. O`zbekiston buyuk kelajak sari. - T.: O`zbekiston, 1999
2. Vesnik D. and Khidekel S. Exercises in Modern English Word-building
3. Арнольд И. В. Стилистика современного английского языка:

⁴ Vesnik D. and Khidekel S. Exercises in Modern English Word-building. - 286p

Стилистика декодирования. 2-е изд., перераб. Л., 1981

4. Иванова И. П., Бурлакова В. В., Почепцов Г. Г. Теоретическая грамматика современного английского языка. М., 1981